

RESEARCH THEORIES OF PHYSICS COURSES IN JAPAN

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The purpose of this study is to explain in-service programs for science and physics teachers in Japan. This study specifically discusses the "course research" approach. "Lesson research" is an approach used in teacher training. Lesson Research was developed in Japan and has been successfully used in teacher training in many countries. Document review, one of the qualitative research methods, was used to collect data for this study conducted in a survey model. When document analysis was carried out in the study, efforts were made to access primary sources, documents were analyzed and data were analyzed and presented. One of the methods that can be used in document review is to consult expert knowledge. In this study, we consulted a Japanese expert and tried to collect relevant and authentic information. At the end of the study, proposals were made for improving the qualifications of science and physics teachers.

Keywords: In-service training, science and physics teachers, course research

Introduction: One approach used in teacher training in Japan is Jugyou kenkyu; It is an approach defined as collaborative research in learning and teaching. Translated as "collaborative research in classroom activities" by Nagoya University Research Group. However, researchers in the United States describe this approach as "lesson learning." In Japan, "Lesson Inquiry" emerged as the foundation of the educational movement to implement student-centered teaching. This is the most common approach to teacher training in Japan. "Lesson research" is an approach that has gained wide influence around the world and is also used by other countries. The phrase "lecture research" is a translation of the Japanese word Jugyokenkyu (jugyo means lesson, kenkyu means study or research). In fact, Jugyokenkyu involves more than just learning lessons. Therefore, when Jugyokenkyu is translated as "lecture study", it does not convey its full meaning.

"Lesson research" is the systematic questioning of teaching practice by examining lessons. These examined lessons are designated as kenkyujugyo in Japanese. Hence, it is the opposite of Jugyokenkyu, meaning a study or course of study. This approach is seen worldwide as an alternative model for schooling

innovation and teacher development. Many researchers have used this method to enrich classroom practice and provide professional development for teachers. Educational researchers and educators in the United States and England see "lesson research" as an alternative approach for teachers who want to study classroom practice and shift the focus from teaching to learning. . Researchers in Thailand and Singapore say that "lesson research" can be a new model in teacher professional development and a useful way to improve teacher quality and student achievement. The Hong Kong Institute of Education uses "lesson research" in teacher training. It is used in professional development of teachers in China, Vietnam, Indonesia, Iran and Korea and has brought a new perspective to the field. There are many types of school-based professional development in Japanese schools. However, jugyou kenkyu is the most meaningful and basic program. Jugyou kenkyu is being developed as "collaborative research in teaching" in various forms.

Generally and systematically, it is a four-step cycle: plan-do-control-act. First, teachers should plan their collaborative research. They must then implement this plan and finally reflect and evaluate the success of the process in the form of a learning review and improvement. With jugyou kenkyu, the classroom is not only a workplace, but also a source of professional development, serving as a model for teachers to achieve meaningful change in their careers. In addition, teachers share responsibility for the teaching and learning process, which includes developing lesson plans, teaching materials, working with students, and assessing students.

The process of "lesson research" begins with the identification of the goals to be achieved at the end of the education. Then teachers start working on the lesson, identifying the necessary strategies to achieve the goal. Teachers plan a lesson in groups and make a detailed lesson plan. After this stage, one of the teachers in the group implements this lesson plan. Other members of the group observe this lesson and take notes on the lesson plan. After this lesson, group members gather to share and discuss their observations. Based on the observations made, the lesson plan is reviewed and necessary changes are made. Another member of the group then implements the new lesson plan in the classroom he/she is teaching, while the other teachers observe the lesson. After the lesson, teachers share their observations, comments and suggestions. Typically, "lesson research" involves 10-15 hours of group meetings over 3-4 weeks, with two lectures held a few days apart. During lesson research, observing teachers observe situations that they do not have the opportunity to

observe when teaching their lessons: what students think, how they interact, what they talk to each other, how much they are interested in learning the concepts presented in the lesson. ready A "course study" consists of a series of planned steps that may last several months or more. It usually includes the following activities:

- Collaborative lesson planning
- Doing the lesson in the classroom
- Get lesson tracking information
- Reflecting, discussing and repeating the lesson
- Redo the lesson

In addition, the "course research" team prepares a report on the work and results of the entire process. This method supports and encourages regular cooperation and solidarity among teachers. Teachers often participate in "lesson research" as part of their training as part of state-sponsored professional development. During their training, prospective teachers prepare for "course research" with a university counselor and a practicing school counselor. The Lesson Study approach, which originated in Japan, challenges experienced teachers to test and improve their teaching practices. The origins of Japanese "lecture research" (sometimes called "research course") date back to the early 1990s. Many "course research" centers have opened in America. "Lesson Research", Jugyou Kenkyu is described as the main teacher training program in the school. In this approach, teachers find opportunities to reflect and create their own responses to the many challenges they face in school and in the classroom. Japanese teachers see professional development and teacher improvement as a lifelong process. They know that experience, self-study, peer critique of their lessons, and self-reflection are important parts of the process. Japanese teachers are interested in long-term self-evaluation and improvement rather than one-off seminars on the latest educational topics. When Japanese teachers are asked what they have learned from the "lesson research" process, most of them say, "My perspective on students is improving."

conclusion

Teacher training in Japan; It is implemented at various levels, including national, regional, city and school. Special attention is paid to in-service professional development practices held in schools. Voluntary working groups are also distinguished in the professional development of teachers in Japan. The state provides financial support for such activities to support volunteer activities. Examples include web pages and blogs created by teachers. In this

way, teachers can share their work with colleagues and have various discussions in the forum section. However, teachers conduct these activities in their own time and at their own discretion. In our age of rapid development of information and technology, such regulation is effective in improving the quality of teachers and, therefore, education. Participating in professional development programs at regular intervals is essential, especially for science and physics teachers, to learn about developments in their fields and teaching methods and techniques. It can be seen that universities in Japan play an important role in teacher training. Universities support the professional development of teachers through programs called "School leaving for post-secondary education" and three- or six-month programs organized in universities. By cooperating with universities, teachers can be improved both in their fields and in the methods and methods of teaching science. This can be achieved by using the knowledge and experience of universities in Japan. Lesson Research, which originated in Japan and is being implemented in many countries, is an effective approach to professional development. This approach has been used successfully in Japan for years. This approach, defined as collaborative research, can be tested in teaching and learning. However, for this it is important to first have a good understanding of the "course research" approach. The goal of this approach is to work collaboratively to prepare an effective lesson plan, to observe and develop this plan based on observations. The main goal is to enable students to learn more effectively.

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